

Urban Agriculture Policy and Governance

Identifying key challenges and strategic priorities in Valladolid, Flanders and Wrocław to inform a deep dive comparative analysis

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Policy & Governance Deep Dive

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Context

FoodCityBoost (FCB) is a European project focused on understanding and improving how we govern and develop agriculture in urban, peri-urban and rural areas by bringing different groups and sectors together. It is a 4-year project (Jan 2024-Dec 2027) involving six living labs (LLs) across Spain, Poland, Belgium, the Netherlands, Bulgaria & Latvia. More information: foodcityboost.eu

Focusing on Valladolid, Flanders and Wrocław, this 'Policy and Governance Deep Dive' task has started to conduct a cross-city comparative analysis into a locally relevant challenge and real-world examples of tackling this. Earlier this year, we completed three in-person and online workshops with a total of 33 local attendees including peri-urban farmers, allotment growers, activists, policymakers, civil society, NGOs and farmers unions.

WELCOME

Research completed

Identified 16 common challenges reported across city-regions through workshops with all six FCB living labs

Hosted strategic prioritization workshops (Flujograma method) with Valladolid, Flanders/Brussels and Wrocław to determine the challenge with most strategic relevance for deeper analysis

This Project

Identify 1-2 challenges with strategic relevance across cities and insights for cross-city and how they related to other challenges

Agriculture for the Future

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What challenge was seen as a priority?

While the outcomes of the strategic mapping differed slightly across contexts (see p.2 + appendix), **lack of coordination and knowledge sharing, and a need for resilient urban agriculture (UA) coalitions** was broadly highlighted as the most urgent and actionable challenge across Valladolid, Wrocław and Flanders/Brussels, and key to unlocking other more complex structural challenges such as land access. Four routes to achieve better coordination were highlighted in workshop discussion:

Bridging urban-rural divides

Participants in Flanders/Brussels highlighted a gap in the goals, experiences and needs of UA actors in cities vs rural areas, whilst in Valladolid loss of cultural connection to the land was seen as undermining support for UA

Resilient UA governance and momentum

Seen as key to ensuring UA stays prioritised despite political cycles, across Valladolid, Flanders and Wrocław, with the former two regions experiencing disruption to policy, funding and momentum to support UA due to recent electoral changes. Potential strategies to maintain UA momentum included building governance mechanisms outside political structures, individual policymakers who champion UA, and a strong grassroots movement.

Knowledge sharing mechanisms

Across Wrocław and Flanders, there was a desire for smoother knowledge sharing mechanisms both within and between policymakers and practitioners.

Multifunctionality

Across Wrocław and Valladolid, building shared recognition for the broad spectrum of UA benefits was seen as key to building coordination across policy and practice.

We want to hear your in-depth views and ideas on these topics!

- Our next steps involve interviewing local actors to get a more detailed account of experiences of and opportunities/strategies for building coordination, knowledge sharing networks, resilient UA coalitions and bridging urban-rural divides.
- This will contribute to a detailed analysis of the needs and possibilities of policy/governance work for urban agriculture at the local/regional levels, culminating with a cross-regional learning session as a webinar or in a similar format.

To find out more, contact your living lab representative or contact Sol soledad.cuevas@cchs.csic.es

Across all workshops, **political will to support UA** was identified as a root challenge but not within the groups' agency to influence directly. More detailed summaries of each workshop are on the following pages.

VALLADOLID WORKSHOP

An in-person 1,5h workshop was facilitated by FCB researchers (Soledad Cuevas and Daniel Lopez-Garcia) and Entretantos living lab rep (Leslie Griffiths). Fittingly, the workshop took place alongside the launch of a book about eco-urbanism, social cooperation and agriculture, 'Huertopias' by author José Luis Fernández Casadevante 'Kois'.

Thirteen participants attended including garden users (3), farmers (3), civil society (2), urban garden network representatives (1), food distribution network member (1).

The method used was less structured for this first workshop. The common urban agriculture policy/governance challenges identified by FCB researchers were presented, and structured discussion used to group challenges and identify links. When deciding which challenge to prioritise, the group often used 'level of agency to influence the challenge' as a criteria to measure whether it was a priority.

The group emphasized a need for coordination across multiple actors, seen as closely linked with building a common understanding of UA's multi-functionality, as well as to a relative loss of cultural connection to "the land" ("cultura de la tierra").

The FCB researchers translated this into the matrix on the next page...

MATRIX

Which UA policy/governance challenge has most strategic relevance in Valladolid?

Within our control

We have some influence over this

Outside of our control

Lack of coherent approach to UA policy and governance

Scattered Competences

Loss of cultural connection to the land

Lack of awareness of young urban people toward rural and agricultural realities

Insufficient communication across civil society groups (and with decision-makers)

WROCŁAW WORKSHOP

An in-person 2.5 hour workshop was followed by a group meal, facilitated by FCB researchers (Charlotte Gallagher Squires, Anton Parisi) and hosted by Fundacja EkoRozwoju (Monika Onyszkiewicz).

Ten local participants attended including policymakers and municipality employees in the areas of Energy & Climate; UA practitioners from community gardens, allotment gardens, urban microforests; UA activists and artists; and UA researchers.

The Flujograma method was used to facilitate strategic prioritisation of the challenges, with the collective agency of the group to influence the challenge used as a key metric to prioritise with. The in-person format and live translator enabled more in-depth discussion. More time would have allowed for a deeper exploration into the 16 challenges and to discuss areas of disagreement, however the in-person format helped speed things up as participants were invited to directly place the challenge cards on the prioritisation matrix over the break.

In Wrocław, **'insufficient knowledge sharing'** both between practitioners and policymakers, and within practitioners doing UA and policymaking working on UA-related policy but from different administrative departments. However, knowledge sharing between practitioners most immediately actionable and relevant challenge, given that the challenges policymakers face are often due to the complexity and inflexible processes associated with working in large institutions. Also seen as important was **recognising multi-functionality** and **lack of long-term strategy beyond electoral cycles**.

Building political will was seen as vital to creating a supportive policy and governance context for UA, however this was seen as difficult to control directly. Participants also called for a more bottom-up approach to funding UA, which recognises the needs and strengths on-the-ground and ensures that funding responds directly to this, rather than employing top-down objectives and ideas of what is needed.

FLANDERS/ BRUSSELS WORKSHOP

This involved an online 2-hour workshop facilitated by FCB researchers (Charlotte Gallagher Squires, Barbara Schroeter and Paula Sanchez Garcia) and hosted by VLM Living lab representative (Kevin Grauwels)

11 local participants; NGOs (3), local action groups (1), farmers (2), researchers (1), Brussels Regional Government (2) and Environment Agency (1).

Time constraints meant that not all topics that came up could be explored in-depth, and the online format limited engagement at times and created challenges when trying to complete the Flujograma matrix with all participants input. In-person options and greater use of breakout rooms will be explored for the future.

'City-rural divide: Shared understanding between policy and practitioners' was added as an underlying cause of uncoordinated policy and governance, describing the gap in perspective, experience and worldview between urban consumers and rural producers, or food producers and policy makers and administration- whom are often concentrated in cities. This was subsequently voted as the most important challenge to prioritise, followed by **insufficient knowledge sharing within and between practitioners and policymakers**. Tackling this challenge was seen a key to ensuring access to land for UA. Lack of political will was seen as a 'critical knot' or root cause which, if changed, could unlock many of the other challenges such as protection of land for UA, long term strategy beyond electoral cycles, fragmentation of responsibility, lack of policy support for commercialisation and access to municipal land within urban centres.

The Flujograma method was applied online with a Zoom Whiteboard. The matrix included the challenge cards prioritised according to level of agency the group felt they had to influence/control (x axis), arrows drawn indicating direction of causal / influencing relationships, and blue post-its indicating which challenges had the most votes in an individual vote.

Which UA policy/governance challenge has most strategic relevance in Flanders?

LESS RELEVANCE

Regulations make it difficult to sell and share UA produce

Waste management

Access to and protection of healthy soils

Access to water for UA

Financial and resource support limited to short-term

Within our control

We have some influence over this

Outside of our control

POLICY GOVERNANCE & PRACTICE RECOMMENDATIONS

The following practices and initiatives are relevant to the findings presented here

and have been selected from a larger systematic review 'Good Practices for UA Governance' conducted by the FoodCityBoost WP4 team and published soon via the FoodCityBoost website:

foodcityboost.eu

Multi-Stakeholder Policy Formulation and Action

A process [outlined by RUAF](#) which includes non-governmental actors in planning, budgeting, policy design, implementation and monitoring. Rural-based groups should be included to overcome the urban-rural inequalities, and the concentration of political/administrative power often seen in cities. This process can also help build a shared vision and positive working relationships between actors to support future UA coordination. Sufficient time, resources and political power should be committed to ensure the process is equitable and genuinely translates contributions into action, so the process builds rather than erodes trust.

Bottom-up, grassroots and practice-led solutions

Hosting working groups, partnerships and networks within NGOs/grassroots groups may increase their resilience to changing political cycles, [provided they are adequately resourced](#). Partnership building across grassroots initiatives can help build a more resilient and coherent UA movement. For example, the [Twinning Programme](#) partners community food organisations (e.g. food banks) in cities with rural farmers to build city-rural cohesion and share knowledge.

Community-based ownership of UA assets

Commoning is an approach to UA governance which adopts shared/public ownership of assets, typically land. Through informal or formal channels, a group or government body creates an organizational structure, legal framework, and common pool of knowledge/resources. At the smaller scale, community gardens may reflect this approach, while at the larger scale, agriculture may be regarded as a public utility or held in [community land trusts](#). This can help build a sense of [civic responsibility and vision for UA](#).

APPENDIX

Challenges longlist (prioritised in bold, additions in red)

Land	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Access to land for UA (for individuals vs collectives; municipality land vs private; city vs. rural) (Val) Protection of land for UA
Selling & sharing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Regulations limit ability to sell and share UA produce Lack of policy support for commercialisation (Val & Fla) Farmers lack time and resources to deliver and distribute produce High cost of UA production makes it unaffordable for many
Multifunctionality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Recognising the full spectrum of UA benefits in policymaking, funding and evaluation (Val, Wro)
Coordination & knowledge sharing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Fragmentation of responsibility Insufficient knowledge sharing (Val, Fla & Wro) City-rural divide* addition in Flanders (also articulated in Valladolid)
Environmental challenges	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Access to water for UA Waste management Accessing and maintaining good quality soils
Short-termism	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of long term strategy beyond electoral cycles (Wro & Fla) Lack of political will to support UA

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Above is a Venn diagram representing the policy/governance related challenges that were seen as priorities by each workshop, with areas of overlap in the centre. Lack of political will is in grey as it was seen as difficult to change, so not a priority. On the right in green, is the thematic challenge areas identified by FCB research and in bold the thematic areas which the prioritised challenges fit into: Multifunctionality; Coordination + knowledge sharing; and short-termism.

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